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Separation Workflow

Overall study design

Title of the study	Lipidomics study of ovarian lipid droplets in <i>Sinonovagula constricta</i>		
Document creation date	03/21/2025	Corresponding Email	2211130112@nbu.edu.cn
Principal investigator	Xuxu Tian	Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Untargeted
Institution	School of Marine Science, Ningbo University	Clinical	No

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	2-phase system	Were internal standards added prior extraction?	No
pH adjustment	None	Special conditions	sonication
2-phase system	BUME	Derivatization	None

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Ammonium formate	MS Level	MS2
Number of separation dimensions	One dimension	Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	1
Separation type 1	LC	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS2	High resolution
Separation mode 1 (liquid)	HILIC	Resolution at m/z 200 at MS2	17500
Detector	Mass spectrometer	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS2	10
MS type	Q	Recording mode of raw data at MS2	Centroid mode
MS vendor	Thermo Scientific	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No
Ion source	ESI		

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Quality control	Yes
Type of Blanks	Solvent blank	Type of QC sample	Sample pool

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	Yes	Precision	Yes
Lipid recovery	Yes	Accuracy	Yes
Dynamic quantification range	Yes	Guidelines followed	None
Limit of quantitation (LOQ)/Limit of detection (LOD)	Yes		

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Available on request	Raw data upload	Available on request
Are metadata available?	Yes	Additional comments	-

Sample Descriptions

Lipid droplets / *Sinonovagula constricta* / ovary

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Additives	None
Provided preanalytical information	-	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Temperature handling original sample	-20 °C	Additional preservation methods	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Biobank samples	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Sample homogenization	No

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) CAR[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	CAR	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Molecular species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	-
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check on:	-		

1) CAR[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-